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Religious Freedom in Angola: A Critical Analysis of the Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19 in Light of the Constitution and Comparative Law.

Summary

Religious freedom is a fundamental right guaranteed by Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic of Angola (CRA). However, the Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19, currently under discussion, introduces significant restrictions, including state accreditation requirements for ministers of worship, control over places of worship, and the possibility of dissolving religious denominations based on subjective criteria. This study critically analyzes the impact of this proposal on religious freedom, comparing it with models adopted in the United States, Brazil, and Portugal. The research shows that, unlike these countries, where there is robust protection of religious freedom, the Angolan proposal moves towards a model of state control, violating constitutional and international human rights principles. It is concluded that religious regulation must balance public order and fundamental rights, guaranteeing plurality and autonomy of religious confessions without undue state intervention.

Keywords

Religious Freedom; State and Religion; Comparative Law; Constitution of Angola; Human Rights; State Regulation of Religion; Religious Public Policies

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1 Introduction

Religious freedom is one of the fundamental pillars of democratic societies, ensuring that individuals and groups can profess and practice their faith without undue interference from the State. In Angola, this guarantee is enshrined in Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic (CRA), which establishes the separation between the State and religious denominations, as well as the right to free exercise of worship. However, the recent Proposal to Amend Law 12/19, which regulates freedom of religion and worship, raises concerns about potential restrictions on these fundamental rights.

This study carries out a critical and comparative analysis of the aforementioned proposal, examining its implications in light of the Angolan Constitution and comparative law, particularly the models adopted by the United States, Brazil and Portugal. The research highlights the inconsistencies between the new legislation and the constitutional principle of religious freedom, showing how state intervention can limit the autonomy of religious denominations and compromise state neutrality in matters of faith and worship.

Furthermore, the study questions whether the proposal really seeks to regulate religious activity in favor of public order or whether it represents a mechanism of political and ideological control over religious organizations. Comparison with international legal systems shows that democratic countries guarantee the coexistence of religious freedom and state security without compromising fundamental rights. Thus, this research aims to contribute to a critical debate on the limits of state intervention in religion and the need to ensure that legislation respects the constitutional rights and guarantees of Angolan citizens.

Through this approach, the work shows that any regulation on religious freedom must balance the need for order and security with the protection of fundamental rights, ensuring that the State does not become an agent of undue restriction of faith and religious organization.

2. Historical Perspective: Relationship between State and Religion since Independence

Since independence in 1975, the relationship between the Angolan State and religious institutions has been marked by periods of tension and cooperation.

2.1. Post-Independence Period and Marxism-Leninism (1975-1991)

After independence, the Popular Movement for the Liberation of Angola (MPLA) adopted a Marxist-Leninist orientation, influencing the state's stance on religion. During this period:

- **State Distrust:** The government viewed religion as a tool of colonialism, especially due to the Catholic Church's association with the Portuguese regime.
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- **State Controls:** In 1978, the MPLA created the National Institute for Religious Affairs, requiring the registration of churches and religious organizations.
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- **Conflicts with the Catholic Church:** In December 1977, Catholic bishops criticized the government for violations of religious freedom, including the nationalization of the educational system and atheist propaganda. The government responded by reaffirming the separation of church and state, but maintained a critical stance toward religious institutions.

2.2. Transition to Religious Pluralism (1991-Present)

With the transition to a market economy and the adoption of a new constitution in 1991, Angola experienced significant changes:

- **Recognition of Religious Freedom:** The 1992 Constitution enshrined freedom of religion, allowing greater religious pluralism.
- **Proliferation of New Confessions:** There has been an increase in the number of churches, especially of Pentecostal and neo-Pentecostal origin, often without adequate regulation.

- **Regulatory Challenges:** The lack of regulation has led the government to seek ways to control the emergence of new confessions, aiming to maintain public order and prevent abuses.

3. Views of Religious Leaders and Jurists on Religious Freedom

The proposed amendment to Law 12/19 has generated debates among religious leaders and lawyers in Angola.

3.1. Criticism of Unrecognized Churches

- **Closure of Places of Worship:** Leaders of unrecognized churches criticized the new law and the closure of places of worship under “Operation Rescue,” arguing that such actions restrict religious freedom.

3.2. Legal Perspective

- **New Legislation:** Lawyer Paulo Dange highlighted that the proposed law brings many new features in relation to current legislation, including a new financing regime for religious institutions and a reduction in the number of signatures required to legalize a religious sect, from 120,000 to 60,000.

The Proposed Amendment to Law No. 12/19, of May 14, on Freedom of Religion and Worship in Angola has generated significant debate. Some critics argue that both the original law and the proposed amendment are unconstitutional, claiming that they are not based on the Constitution. On the other hand, supporters of the proposal claim that the amendments aim to strengthen the country in terms of designating entities linked to terrorism and its financing, as well as the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction. Deputy Elizandra Coelho highlighted that the changes to the law stem from Angola’s recent evaluation by the Financial Action Task Force (FATF), resulting in the need to adjust the law. These debates reflect the complexity of balancing religious freedom with national security and compliance with international standards. Ongoing discussion among legal experts, religious leaders and legislators is essential to ensure that the legislation respects the fundamental rights enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Angola.

4. Practical Impact of Implementing the New Law

The implementation of the Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19 may have several implications for religious denominations in Angola.

4.1. Prohibition of Worship in Certain Places

- **Space Limitations:** The proposal foresees a ban on holding religious services in homes, backyards and warehouses, which may affect religious communities that use these spaces for their activities.

4.2. Requirements for Recognition

- **Administrative Requirements:** The reduction in the number of signatures required for official recognition of a religious denomination may facilitate the legalization of new churches, but still represents a challenge for smaller groups.

4.3. Supervision and Control

- **Government Operations:** The continuation of operations such as "Operation Rescue" indicates an active stance by the government in monitoring religious activities, which can be seen as interference in freedom of worship.

5. Biblical Perspective on Religious Freedom

Religious freedom is a fundamental right rooted not only in human law but also in Christian theology. The Bible provides a strong foundation for freedom of conscience, worship, and the separation of religious and governmental authority. Throughout both the Old and New Testaments, biblical figures resisted state-imposed religious restrictions, affirming the principle that faith should never be dictated by earthly authorities.

5.1. Theological Foundations of Religious Freedom

The Bible repeatedly emphasizes freedom of worship and conscience, highlighting that faith is a personal relationship with God, not something to be coerced by the state.

One of the clearest statements of separation between religion and state authority comes from Jesus Christ Himself in Matthew 22:21, where He declares:

"Give to Caesar what is Caesar's and to God what is God's."

This statement affirms the distinction between earthly governments and divine authority. Jesus acknowledges that while civil governments have their place in organizing society, they must not infringe upon a person's devotion to God. This verse is fundamental in Christian thought regarding religious liberty because it establishes that political power should not dictate matters of faith.

The Apostle Paul further expands on this concept in Galatians 5:1, where he writes:

"It is for freedom that Christ has set us free. Stand firm, then, and do not let yourselves be burdened again by a yoke of slavery." Paul teaches that faith should be practiced freely, without oppression or coercion. His writings also indicate that religious freedom is not just a social or political issue but a spiritual reality, where every believer must have the autonomy to serve God according to their convictions.

5.1.1. Old Testament and Religious Freedom

The Old Testament presents numerous examples of governmental oppression against worshippers of the true God, demonstrating that state-imposed restrictions on faith are a recurring historical issue. One of the most striking examples is found in the Book of Daniel (Daniel 3 & 6), where King Nebuchadnezzar and later King Darius attempted to regulate worship:

- Daniel's three friends (Shadrach, Meshach, and Abednego) were thrown into a fiery furnace for refusing to bow before the golden idol of Nebuchadnezzar (Daniel 3).
- Daniel himself was cast into the lion's den because he continued to pray to the God of Israel despite King Darius' decree that prohibited prayers to any god except the king (Daniel 6).

Both instances demonstrate government efforts to control religious expression, and both resulted in divine intervention in favor of the persecuted believers. These stories reinforce the

biblical principle that faith is to be obeyed above human laws when the two come into conflict. Another significant example is found in the Exodus narrative, where Moses confronted Pharaoh to demand that the Israelites be allowed to worship God freely. In Exodus 5:1, Moses commands Pharaoh:

"Let my people go, so that they may hold a festival to me in the wilderness."

Pharaoh's resistance led to divine judgment, illustrating that governments that oppress religious freedom ultimately stand in opposition to God's will.

5.1.2. New Testament and the Early Church

The New Testament provides further evidence that early Christians resisted unjust religious restrictions.

In Acts 5:29, when Peter and the apostles were ordered by the Sanhedrin to stop preaching about Christ, they responded:

"We must obey God rather than human beings."

This statement embodies the Christian stance on religious oppression—while believers respect governing authorities, they cannot comply with laws that contradict their faith. The Roman Empire's persecution of Christians further highlights the dangers of state interference in religious affairs. Early Christians refused to worship the emperor, leading to widespread persecution under emperors such as Nero, Domitian, and Diocletian.

The persecution of Christians in the early church closely mirrors the restrictions proposed in Angola's Law 12/19, where the government seeks to regulate and potentially close religious institutions based on its own subjective criteria. History has proven that when the state interferes with faith, it inevitably leads to injustice and persecution.

5.2. How Christian Theology Supports Religious Freedom

From a theological perspective, religious freedom is rooted in God's design for humanity:

a) The Image of God (Imago Dei) – Human Dignity and Free Worship:

Genesis 1:26-27 states that human beings are created in the image of God, giving each person inherent dignity and autonomy. This means that faith must be a voluntary act—forced worship is meaningless in God's eyes.

b) Free Will as a Biblical Principle:

Throughout Scripture, God allows people to choose whether or not to follow Him. In Deuteronomy 30:19, Moses tells Israel:

"I have set before you life and death, blessings and curses. Now choose life, so that you and your children may live."

This reflects the fundamental principle of religious liberty: people must have the freedom to choose their faith without state interference.

After understanding the historical evolution of the relationship between the State and religion in Angola, it becomes essential to analyze how the regulation of religious freedom is treated in different international legal contexts. The comparison between Angola, the United States, Brazil, and Portugal allows us to identify global patterns of protection of religious freedom and to verify whether the Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19 aligns with these democratic models or whether it represents a setback in the fundamental right to belief and worship. While countries such as the United States and Brazil adopt a more liberal and guarantor approach, allowing the operation of religious confessions with minimal state interference, Portugal establishes regulatory mechanisms without compromising the autonomy of churches. In contrast, Angola has moved in a more restrictive direction, imposing strict bureaucratic requirements, control over the structure of religions, and penalties that can directly affect freedom of worship. Thus, the comparative analysis not only highlights the differences in approach, but also allows for a critical reflection on the impact of the proposed restrictions and the need to ensure a balance between regulation and religious freedom.

6. International Comparative Framework of Religious Freedom

Table 1.

Criterion	United States us	Brazil BR	Portugal PT	Angola (Article 41 of the CRA) AO	Angola (Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19 - 2024) 🚧
Main legal basis	📄 First Amendment to the U.S. Constitution (1791)	📄 Federal Constitution (Article 5, items VI to VIII) + Law 10.825/2003	📄 Portuguese Constitution (Article 41) + Religious Freedom Law (Law No. 16/2001)	📄 Constitution of Angola (Article 41)	📄 Proposal to amend Law 12/19 (2024)
Separation of Church and State	✅ Yes (more rigid model)	✅ Yes	✅ Yes	✅ Yes	❌ The State begins to interfere in the organization and doctrine of churches (Articles 31, 33 and 46)
Control over religious confessions	❌ No control	⚖️ Registration with the Ministry of Justice for tax benefits, but without doctrinal interference	⚖️ Optional registration for tax benefits, without doctrinal interference	❌ No control	🚧 Requires presence in all provinces for recognition (Articles 43 and 46)
Requirements for Ministers of Worship	❌ None	❌ None	❌ None	❌ None	🚧 Requires higher theological training (Bachelor's degree) for religious leaders to be recognized (Articles 31 and 33)
Monitoring of religious	❌ There is none	❌ There is none	❌ There is none	❌ There is none	🚧 The State may monitor religious

doctrines by the State					doctrines and practices (Articles 42 and 48)
Worship services in homes or informal locations	✔ Allowed	✔ Allowed	✔ Allowed	✔ Allowed	🚫 Prohibited in homes, backyards, warehouses, etc. (Article 26, points 5 and 6)
Authorization for entry of foreign ministers	✔ No requirements	✔ No requirements	✔ No requirements	✔ No requirements	🚫 Requires accreditation and authorization from the State (Article 33-BIS, points 2.a and 2.b)
Possibility of revocation of churches	✘ There is none	✘ There is none	✘ There is none	✘ There is none	🚫 Recognition may be revoked based on subjective criteria (e.g. "family breakdown") (Article 48, paragraphs q, res)
Creation of new religions	✔ Free process, no requirements	✔ Simple and non-discriminatory process	✔ Simple and non-discriminatory process	✔ Free process	🚫 High degree of state control over new religious denominations (Articles 42, 43 and 46)
Tax benefits for religions	✔ Automatic, no registration required	✔ For registered churches	✔ For registered churches	✔ For registered churches	🚫 Mandatory registration to have any legal and tax rights (Article 20, point 5)
Religious education in public schools	✘ Forbidden	✔ Allowed (optional and non-denominational)	✘ Not allowed (except in	✘ Not allowed	🚫 The State may require specific training for religious

			specific cases)		teachers (Article 33)
Possibility of churches being closed by the State	✗ There is none	🚫 Possible closure of churches due to "internal conflicts" or "ritual practices that cause social destabilization" (Article 53, paragraphs d and e)			

7. Critical Discussion of the Comparative Chart

A comparison between the models of religious freedom adopted in the United States, Brazil, Portugal and Angola reveals different approaches to the relationship between State and Religion. The countries analyzed vary between a completely free model (USA), an intermediate model (Brazil), a regulated model but respecting religious freedom (Portugal) and the original Angolan model, which follows constitutional principles of separation between State and Churches. The Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19, however, introduces a highly restrictive model, approaching systems that limit religious autonomy and impose state control over confessions.

7.1. United States (Absolute Freedom Model)

- ✓ No registration requirements or government control over churches.
- ✓ The government cannot interfere in the selection of religious leaders.
- ✓ Full protection against government closures.
- ✓ The First Amendment to the Constitution prevents any regulation that limits faith and worship.

7.2. Brazil (Intermediate Model, with Guarantees of Freedom)

- ✓ Church registration is not mandatory, but it offers tax benefits.
- ✓ Complete freedom of worship in any space, without restrictions on locations.
- ✓ The State does not interfere in doctrines or the choice of religious leaders.
- ✓ Churches can operate without state regulation, as long as they do not violate civil and criminal laws.

7.3. Portugal (Regulated Model, but Guaranteeing Religious Freedom):

- ✓ Registration is only required for tax benefits and legal recognition.
- ✓ No restrictions on places of worship. Churches can operate freely.
- ✓ The State does not interfere in the internal organization of churches nor does it require specific qualifications for religious leaders.
- ✓ Regulation exists for administrative purposes, without compromising the right to belief.

7.4. Angola (Article 41 of the Constitution - Original Model of Separation of Church and State):

- ✓ Ensures the separation between State and Churches, ensuring government neutrality.
- ✓ No restrictions on places of worship, allowing freedom of organization.
- ✓ No formal requirement for accreditation of religious leaders.
- ✓ Protects the existence of religious confessions without direct government monitoring.

7.5. Angola (Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19 - Restrictive and State Control Model):

- ✗ The State gains control over religious doctrines and can revoke the recognition of churches.
- ✗ It requires pastors and religious leaders to have higher theological training to exercise their ministry.
- ✗ It prohibits worship in informal places, such as homes and backyards, limiting the religious freedom of smaller communities.

✗ It authorizes the closure of churches for broad and subjective reasons, including "social disruption".

✗ It imposes mandatory accreditation for foreign ministers, making their entry and stay in the country conditional on state approval.

8. The Social and Legal Consequences of Restricting Religious Freedom

History has repeatedly shown that restricting faith leads to persecution, social instability, and political oppression. Governments that attempt to control religious practice often violate fundamental human rights, creating division and unrest within their societies.

Angola's proposed Law 12/19 introduces severe state control over religious institutions, granting the government the power to approve or reject clergy, regulate places of worship, and dissolve religious groups. These measures undermine democracy, contradict Angola's constitutional protections (Article 41 of the CRA), and violate international human rights standards such as Article 18 of the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which guarantees:

"Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience, and religion."

Additionally, the economic consequences of restricting religious institutions cannot be ignored. Churches play a crucial role in providing education, healthcare, and social services, particularly in communities where state services are lacking. By limiting religious organizations, Angola risks weakening its social infrastructure, negatively impacting education, charity work, and humanitarian aid.

Furthermore, historical precedents show that excessive state control over religion leads to conflict. Countries like the Soviet Union, China, and Nazi Germany suppressed religious groups to solidify government power, leading to widespread persecution, human rights abuses, and internal resistance. Angola must learn from these historical failures and avoid policies that promote oppression rather than social harmony.

A truly democratic and stable society must protect religious freedom, not control it. If Angola enforces this law, it risks not only international condemnation but also domestic unrest and

economic hardship. Therefore, for the sake of social cohesion, legal integrity, and human rights, this law must not be enacted.

9. Critical Reflection

The analysis of the comparative table shows that the Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19 imposes unprecedented restrictions on religious freedom in Angola, contradicting the principle of separation between State and Religion established in Article 41 of the Constitution. Furthermore, by requiring state control over churches, the closure of places of worship and mandatory theological qualification for religious leaders, the proposal brings Angola closer to authoritarian models of religious regulation, distancing it from democratic countries that guarantee freedom of belief and religious organization. However, we recognize the state's efforts to seek adjustments to religious freedom, but these must be carried out under the foundations of the Constitution of the Republic of Angola. If implemented, the new legislation could represent a setback in religious freedom, creating disproportionate barriers to the practice of faith and subjecting religious confessions to government control.

10. Conclusions

- a) The Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19 in Angola represents a significant and restrictive change compared to the models adopted in Portugal, Brazil and the United States. By imposing strict requirements for the recognition of churches, limiting freedom of worship in informal settings and making the actions of religious leaders conditional on state approval, the proposal directly interferes with the fundamental right to religious freedom, guaranteed by Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic of Angola. If approved, this legislation will create an environment of state control over religious confessions, weakening the separation between State and Church and compromising the diversity of religious expression in the country.
- b) The relationship between the Angolan State and religious denominations has undergone a historical evolution, from a period of mistrust and repression in the post-independence period to contemporary attempts at regulation and control. Although the Proposed Amendment to Law 12/19 appears to seek a balance between religious freedom and public order, its excessive measures jeopardize the fundamental principles of the rule of law by granting the government the power to monitor, restrict and dissolve religious denominations based on broad and subjective criteria.
- c) It is essential that any reform of the legislation on religious freedom be conducted on the basis of constitutional principles, respect for religious diversity and Angola's international human rights commitments. The true protection of public order should not be confused with the arbitrary restriction of faith and worship, as this risks compromising social stability, democracy and freedom of conscience in the country.

11. Recommendation:

A more balanced model aligned with democratic principles would be similar to that adopted in Brazil or Portugal, where churches are registered for administrative and fiscal purposes, but without state interference in internal organization, doctrine and freedom of worship. This model ensures compliance with the law without violating the fundamental rights of religious denominations.

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